

Prompt Model Canvas

Designed by:

Designed for:

Date:

Goal

Define the purpose of the prompt. It is the action you want the AI to perform or the information you want to obtain.

Examples:

"Provide an overview of the concept of strategic management."

"Explain the steps to creating an effective business plan."

"Create a post for Instagram about the best practices in project management."

Brand Persona

Describe the image and voice of the brand or company that is using the AI. This should be aligned with the brand's identity and the way it communicates with its customers.

Examples:

"A business consulting firm that values precision, clarity, and efficiency."

"An innovative startup that takes a laid-back and friendly approach to business management."

"An academic institution that communicates in a formal and informative way, focusing on knowledge and learning."

Output format

Define the desired format and structure for the AI's response. This can include the type of language, organization of information, etc.

Examples:

"In the first two slides discuss the problem, from slide 3 to 8 talk about the solution, on the ninth slide conclude the reasoning, and finally, create a call to action."

"Step by step explanations, with each step clearly outlined and explained."

"Responses in a question-and-answer format, with the question clearly restated before the answer."

Specifications

Define details (and limits) such as the number of characters, tone of voice, formality, use of jargon, etc. These specifications help shape the AI's response.

Examples:

"The AI should provide a response that is friendly and accessible, creating a welcoming environment for the user. The response can be longer, up to 1000 characters, allowing for a more detailed explanation. The use of management jargon is permitted, as it can help provide a more accurate and professional response."

"The AI should provide a response that is concise and direct, getting straight to the point. The response should be limited to 280 characters, similar to a tweet, to ensure that the information is conveyed quickly and efficiently. The response should avoid the use of jargon or technical language to ensure it is understandable to all users, regardless of their knowledge in management."

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Context

Provide additional information that can help the AI generate a more accurate and relevant response.

Examples:

"The user is seeking to understand the importance of strategic planning in a startup."

"The brand is a technology startup that promotes agility and flexibility, and the user wants to know how to implement an agile work culture."

"Considering the growing adoption of remote work due to the COVID-19 pandemic."

AI Role

Define the personality and communication style of the AI. It can include characteristics such as formality, humor, seriousness, etc.

Examples:

"A polite and formal virtual assistant, with deep knowledge in business management."

"A friendly and approachable business consultant, with a practical approach to management."

"A journalist specialized in strategic management, who communicates in a clear and concise manner, without jargon, that a 10-year-old can understand."

Audience

Identify the target audience for the purpose of this content. Include information about who will receive the result generated by the AI, their needs, level of knowledge, etc.

Examples:

"Early-career entrepreneurs seeking guidance in business management."

"Experienced project managers looking for new strategies and approaches."

"Business students who need clear and concise explanations about management concepts."

Output Examples

Provide examples of what you would like the AI's response to be like. This helps the AI understand what is expected of it.

Enter examples of responses that you find interesting and ask the AI to follow the same pattern/model.

